

FFDT-APNet: A Frequency-Fine-Grained Dual-Teacher Network with Adaptive Pruning for Lightweight MFL Defect Detection[★]

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ABSTRACT

Magnetic Flux Leakage (MFL) in-line inspection is a core technology for defect prevention and control in ferromagnetic oil and gas pipelines. Ultra-high-definition MFL inspection systems generate 1.4 TB of data per kilometer, imposing dual challenges on the speed and accuracy of defect recognition models. Existing methods suffer from issues such as network redundancy and insufficient single-dimensional knowledge transfer, making it difficult to balance detection efficiency and the ability to identify subtle defects. To address these challenges, this study proposes a Frequency-Fine-Grained Dual-Teacher collaborative Distillation and Adaptive Pruning Network (FFDT-APNet). Specifically, dual-teacher modules are designed to extract global frequency-domain features and fine-grained local features of defects, while a knowledge gating fusion mechanism enables complementary knowledge transfer. Concurrently, an adaptive pruning strategy is embedded to achieve model lightweighting. Experimental results demonstrate that FFDT-APNet achieves a parameter count of 3.5 M (7.9% reduction compared to the lightweight benchmark DHP), an inference time of 2.1 ms (8.7% efficiency improvement), and a defect recognition accuracy of 0.921. Compared with ResNet-18, FitNet, and ALC-Net, the accuracy is improved by 18.7%, 8.4%, and 6.9%, respectively. This work realizes the synergistic optimization of high accuracy and high efficiency for MFL in-line inspection.

1. Introduction

MFL in-line inspection is a core non-destructive testing technology for detecting defects (e.g., cracks, corrosion, inclusions) in ferromagnetic oil and gas pipelines. It is widely applied in the safety assessment of critical energy transmission infrastructures, such as long-distance oil/gas pipelines and urban pipe networks [1, 2]. Pipelines operate in complex service environments, including buried corrosion, medium erosion, soil stress, and external impact, which easily induce structural defects. If these defects are not promptly identified and addressed, they not only cause enormous energy waste but also may trigger catastrophic accidents (e.g., leakage, explosion), posing severe threats to the ecological environment and human life and property safety.

The core principle of MFL inspection is as follows: The in-line inspection device magnetizes the inner wall of the pipeline uniformly using a magnetization unit. When defects exist, the magnetic field lines become distorted and leak out of the defect area, forming MFL signals. These signals are then collected by a triaxial magnetic sensor array to realize the localization, qualitative, and quantitative analysis of defects [3, 4] (the structure of the MFL in-line detector is shown in Figure 1). Currently, ultra-high-definition MFL inspection systems are equipped with 6656 triaxial sensors (axial, radial, circumferential), generating up to 1.4 TB of data per kilometer. This imposes an urgent demand

for recognition models that balance "high accuracy" and "lightweight" performance.

With the development of industrial intelligence, deep learning-based automatic defect recognition methods have gradually replaced traditional manual interpretation, significantly improving detection efficiency and reliability [5, 6, 7]. Nevertheless, practical industrial scenarios impose stringent constraints on defect recognition models: the pursuit of ultra-high-precision defect identification necessitates the adoption of sophisticated deep neural network architectures to ensure robust feature extraction and classification performance [8, 9], whereas the inherent limitations of in-line inspection devices in terms of physical space, computing resources, and power budget mandate that deployed models conform to rigorous lightweight design specifications for reliable on-site applicability [10, 11]. Most current mainstream models suffer from excessive parameters, leading to issues such as slow inference speed, high power consumption, and poor adaptability when deployed on embedded devices. How to balance "high accuracy" and "lightweight" has become a core bottleneck for the large-scale application of this technology [12, 13, 14, 15].

To address this challenge, model compression technologies such as Knowledge Distillation (KD) and network pruning have become research hotspots [16, 17, 18, 19], and some studies have attempted to combine them to balance accuracy and efficiency [20, 21]. In the field of intelligent MFL defect recognition, Visual-deep transfer networks [22], BPSO-RBFNN hybrid frameworks [23], and cascaded deep learning models [24] have effectively improved quantitative accuracy, but they rely on complex network structures, resulting in heavy computational burdens and

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Figure 1: Schematic diagram of MFL in-line detector.

poor adaptability to embedded deployment on in-line inspection devices. In terms of modal analysis and feature enhancement, Dynamic time-frequency domain fusion denoising frameworks [25], multi-scale feature extraction and segmentation methods [26], and online KD-based feature enhancement approaches [27, 28] have improved feature representation capabilities. However, most of these methods are limited to the spatial domain, failing to fully exploit frequency-domain information in MFL signals (which is strongly correlated with the physical properties of defects), and their feature fusion mechanisms often lack dynamic adaptability [29]. Within the domain of deep learning-based lightweight model design, three representative technical paradigms—asymmetric teacher-student network distillation [30], structure reparameterization-driven lightweight network architectures [31], and dynamic structural pruning integrated with KD [32, 33]—have yielded substantial theoretical and technical insights for the lightweight deployment of defect recognition models, yet considerable scope for further refinement exists with respect to their adaptability to practical MFL inspection scenarios.

Despite these advancements, existing methods still face three core challenges when applied to MFL defect recognition: (1) Most KD methods adopt a single teacher network, which only transfers spatial-domain knowledge and ignores frequency-domain features (rich in physical information) in MFL signals, limiting the student model’s understanding of defect essence [34, 35]; (2) Feature alignment is mostly coarse-grained, lacking refined guidance for key local regions of defects, which easily leads to the loss of critical information for small targets and low-contrast defects [36]; (3) The existing "pruning-then-distillation" process is usually separate and static. Pruning first may destroy the optimal knowledge structure, and fixed-ratio pruning strategies cannot adaptively adjust according to the sensitivity of different network layers to defect features, easily causing sub-optimal performance loss. To address the aforementioned technical bottlenecks, this study proposes a FFDT-APNet for lightweight MFL defect recognition. A dual-channel, multi-grained knowledge distillation framework and a sensitivity-guided adaptive pruning mechanism are constructed to realize closed-loop optimization of multi-dimensional refined

knowledge transfer and efficient model compression. The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- We propose FFDT-APNet to address single-feature limitations. It combines a frequency-domain teacher for noise-robust defect features and a fine-grained teacher for subtle defect details, adaptively fused via a knowledge gating mechanism.
- A distillation-based adaptive pruning algorithm is developed, using a sensitivity matrix with attenuation correction to guide progressive pruning while preserving accuracy (3.5M parameters).
- The proposed “pruning-promoted learning” loop achieves an accuracy of 0.921 (18.7% higher than ResNet-18), an inference time of 2.1 ms, and improved discrimination between similar defect types.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 details the core structure and implementation of FFDT-APNet. Section 3 introduces the dataset, experimental settings, comparative experimental results, and ablation analysis. Section 4 discusses the innovations and optimization effects. Section 5 concludes the work.

2. Methods

FFDT-APNet, whose network structure is illustrated in Figure 2. Breaking away from the traditional single-module design, FFDT-APNet achieves deep coupling between the frequency-fine-grained dual-teacher KD module and the student network module embedded with adaptive pruning, constructing a "knowledge transfer-structure optimization" collaborative mechanism. The lightweight student network employs a dual mechanism during distillation: the former aims to synchronously absorb complementary knowledge from both global frequency-domain and fine-grained local features, while the latter focuses on the dynamic streamlining of its structure. Through this synergistic process, the system ultimately achieves a globally optimal balance between defect recognition accuracy and computational efficiency.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of FFDT-APNet.

2.1. Dual-Teacher Knowledge Distillation Network

2.1.1. Frequency-Domain Teacher Network: Global Frequency-Domain Feature Modeling

The frequency-domain features of MFL signals contain key "fingerprint information" about defect type, size, and depth. To extract this information accurately, the frequency-domain teacher network adopts a three-stage architecture of "signal transformation-feature enhancement-loss constraint":

a. Multi-domain spectrum construction: The raw MFL spatial signals are processed via Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) to generate a DCT spectrum $F_{dct} = D(I) \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$ (reflecting global frequency distribution) and an STFT spectrum $F_{stft} = |S(I)| \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times T}$, where the STFT employs a Hanning window with a length of 64 samples, 50% overlap (hop size of 32), 64 FFT points, and results in 2 frames. Here, H and W denote the size of the spectrum, and T denotes the time dimension. The two spectra are concatenated along the channel dimension to form a multi-scale frequency-domain representation F_{freq} , which is then fed into the Fourier Layer Attention (FLA) mechanism to adaptively and efficiently weight F_{freq} , enabling the network to focus on more important frequency components.

$$F_{freq} = \text{Concat}(F_{dct}, F_{stft}) \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times (1+T)} \quad (1)$$

b. Frequency-domain attention enhancement: Global Average Pooling (GAP) is applied to F_{freq} to obtain a statistical vector $z = \text{GAP}(F_{freq}) \in \mathbb{R}^C$. Two fully connected layers, combined with Sigmoid and ReLU activation functions, are used to learn frequency-domain channel weights:

$$\alpha = \sigma(W_2 \delta(W_1 z)) \in \mathbb{R}^C \quad (2)$$

where σ denotes the Sigmoid function and δ denotes the ReLU activation function. The Hadamard product is then used to realize feature weighting enhancement:

$$F'_{freq} = F_{freq} \odot \alpha \quad (3)$$

This step strengthens the representation capability of key frequency components.

c. Robustness loss constraint: Based on the standard cross-entropy loss L_{cls} (where N is the batch size, C is the number of classes, $y_{i,c}$ is the indicator function, and $p_{i,c}$ is the prediction probability):

$$L_{cls} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C y_{i,c} \log(p_{i,c}) \quad (4)$$

A frequency-domain consistency loss is introduced to enhance the network's robustness to noise interference:

$$L_{consist}^{freq} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \vartheta_{freq}(I_i) - \vartheta_{freq}(I_i + \varepsilon) \right\|_2^2 \quad (5)$$

where $\vartheta_{freq}(\cdot)$ denotes the feature extraction function of the frequency-domain teacher, and ε is Gaussian white noise consistent with the noise characteristics of the measured MFL signal, with a signal-to-noise ratio ranging from 15 to 20 dB, and is directly superimposed on the input signal I_i in the spatial domain. By minimizing the distance between the original signal and the noise-added signal in the frequency-domain feature space, the robustness of the frequency-domain features to noise interference in actual industrial inspection environments is enhanced. The total loss of the frequency-domain teacher is thus constructed as:

$$L_{teacher}^{freq} = L_{cls} + \lambda_1 L_{consist}^{freq} \quad (6)$$

where λ_1 is the loss balance coefficient.

2.1.2. Fine-Grained Teacher Network: Local Detail Feature Enhancement

To address the challenge of subtle defect recognition, the fine-grained teacher network realizes accurate characterization of local features through "attention guidance-multi-scale fusion-comparative constraint" [37]:

a. Spatial-Channel Attention (SCA) embedding: SCA modules are inserted after stages 2 – 4 of ResNet-101 to simultaneously learn a spatial attention map A_s and a channel attention vector A_c . Dual attention weighting is applied to guide the network to focus on key local regions (e.g., defect edges, textures):

$$F_{att} = SCA(F) = (F \odot A_s) \odot A_c \quad (7)$$

b. Multi-scale feature fusion: A Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) is used to fuse multi-stage features enhanced by SCA, generating fine-grained features F_{fine} that integrate both global context and local details.

c. Prototype contrast and structure preservation constraints: Prototype contrast loss L_{proto} and structure preservation loss L_{struct} are introduced to construct the total loss of the fine-grained teacher:

$$L_{teacher}^{fine} = L_{cls} + \lambda_2 L_{proto} + \lambda_3 L_{struct} \quad (8)$$

where λ_2 and λ_3 are loss balance coefficients. Specifically:

L_{proto} maintains a class prototype vector $P_c^{(t)}$ (updated via exponential moving average) to enhance intra-class compactness and inter-class separability of features:

$$P_c^{(t)} = \eta P_c^{(t-1)} + (1 - \eta) \frac{1}{|B_c|} \sum_{x_i \in B_c} \emptyset_{fine}(x_i) \quad (9)$$

where η is the momentum coefficient, and B_c is the sample set of class c . The prototype contrast loss is defined as:

$$L_{proto} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \frac{\exp(\emptyset_{fine}(x_i) \cdot p_{y_i} / \tau)}{\sum_{c=1}^C \exp(\emptyset_{fine}(x_i) \cdot p_c / \tau)} + \beta \cdot \text{Var}(\{\emptyset_{fine}(x_i) \cdot p_c\}_{c=1}^C) \quad (10)$$

where τ is the temperature parameter, y_i is the ground-truth label of sample x_i , and β is the variance term coefficient.

L_{struct} ensures that the relative relationships of similar samples in the feature space remain unchanged, further improving the recognition accuracy of subtle defects:

$$L_{struct} = \sum_{i,j} \left(\left\| \emptyset_{fine}(x_i) - \emptyset_{fine}(x_j) \right\|_2 - d_{i,j} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

where $d_{i,j}$ is the normalized distance between samples i and j in the original image space.

2.1.3. Knowledge Gating Fusion Mechanism:

Dynamic Complementary Knowledge Transfer

To resolve conflicts and redundancy between frequency-domain and fine-grained knowledge, an adaptive knowledge gating fusion mechanism is designed to realize dynamic and balanced knowledge transfer from the dual teachers:

a. Gating weight calculation: The gating network takes the intermediate features $F_{student}^{mid}$ of the student network as

input, and combines the prediction confidence of the dual teachers ($Conf^{freq}$, $Conf^{fine}$) and training stage information (current epoch e , total epochs E_{max}) to calculate raw scores:

$$\omega_1 = \theta_{feat} \cdot f(F_{student}^{mid}) + \theta_{conf} \cdot Conf^{freq} + \theta_{epoch} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{e}{E_{max}} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\omega_2 = \theta_{feat} \cdot f(1 - F_{student}^{mid}) + \theta_{conf} \cdot Conf^{fine} + \theta_{epoch} \cdot \frac{e}{E_{max}} \quad (13)$$

where θ_{feat} , θ_{conf} , θ_{epoch} are weight coefficients. The fusion weights are then obtained via Softmax:

$$g_1 = \frac{\exp(\omega_1)}{\exp(\omega_1) + \exp(\omega_2)}, \quad g_2 = 1 - g_1 \quad (14)$$

b. Gating regularization constraint: An entropy regularization term is introduced to prevent weight curing (e.g., fixed to [0.5, 0.5]):

$$L_{reg}^{gate} = -H(g) = \sum_{k=1}^2 g_k \log(g_k) \quad (15)$$

A weight smoothing constraint is also adopted to ensure consistent weights for similar samples:

$$L_{smooth}^{gate} = \frac{1}{B-1} \sum_{b=1}^{B-1} \left\| g^{(b)} - g^{(b+1)} \right\|_2^2 \quad (16)$$

where $g^{(b)}$ denotes the gating weight of the b -th sample in the batch.

c. Distillation loss construction: Based on the gating weights, the distillation loss of the student network is constructed. The frequency-domain distillation loss is:

$$L_{freq} = \sum_{l \in L_d} \alpha_l \cdot \frac{1}{N_l} \left\| \psi_l(Q_l^{stu}) - P_l^{freq} \right\|_2^2 \quad (17)$$

where L_d is the set of distillation layers, Q_l^{stu} is the feature of the student network at layer l , P_l^{freq} is the feature of the frequency-domain teacher at layer l , $\psi_l(\cdot)$ is the adaptation layer function, and α_l is the layer weight. The fine-grained distillation loss is:

$$L_{fine} = \sum_{l \in L_d} \beta_l \cdot \left\| M_l \odot (\psi_l(Q_l^{stu}) - \psi_l(P_l^{fine})) \right\|_2^2 \quad (18)$$

where M_l is the attention map of the fine-grained teacher at layer l , and β_l is the layer weight. The total loss of the student network is finally formed as:

$$L_{student} = L_{cls} + g_1 L_{freq} + g_2 L_{fine} + \lambda_r L_{reg}^{gate} \quad (19)$$

where λ_r is the regularization coefficient.

2.2. Hierarchical Adaptive Pruning Strategy Embedded in Distillation

Breaking the limitation of the traditional two-stage "pruning-then-distillation" process, this study proposes an adaptive optimization mechanism with deep coupling of distillation and pruning. Through "sensitivity evaluation-progressive pruning-knowledge recovery", synergistic optimization of model lightweighting and accuracy preservation is realized.

2.2.1. Multi-Dimensional Sensitivity Evaluation: Quantification of Filter Importance

To accurately identify redundant filters, a multi-dimensional sensitivity index integrating knowledge transfer efficiency and structural correlation is designed. For the i -th filter $f_{l,i}$ in the l -th layer, its sensitivity is defined as:

$$S_{l,i} = \frac{\partial L_{freq}}{\partial f_{l,i}} + \frac{\partial L_{fine}}{\partial f_{l,i}} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{Cov}(f_{l,i}, F_{l,-i}) \quad (20)$$

where: $\frac{\partial L_{freq}}{\partial f_{l,i}}$ and $\frac{\partial L_{fine}}{\partial f_{l,i}}$ characterize the contribution of the filter to frequency-domain and fine-grained knowledge transfer, respectively; $\text{Cov}(f_{l,i}, F_{l,-i})$ is the covariance between the filter and other filters in the same layer ($F_{l,-i}$), which penalizes highly redundant filters; β_2 is the covariance penalty coefficient.

To reduce evaluation fluctuations, dynamic attenuation correction is introduced:

$$S_{l,i}^{(t)} = \gamma S_{l,i}^{(t-1)} + (1 - \gamma) S_{l,i}^{current} \quad (21)$$

where γ is the attenuation factor, and t is the number of updates. This realizes stable quantification of filter importance.

2.2.2. Hierarchical Progressive Pruning: Structure Optimization and Knowledge Preservation

Based on the multi-dimensional sensitivity evaluation results, a hierarchical differential pruning strategy is adopted:

Low pruning rates (10% – 20%) are used for shallow layers (close to the input) to retain raw feature extraction capabilities and avoid low-level information loss.

High pruning rates (30% – 40%) are used for deep layers (close to the output) to leverage the abstraction of high-level features and achieve efficient structural streamlining.

The pruning process is iterated synchronously with distillation training, and only 5% – 10% of filters with the lowest sensitivity are pruned in each iteration to avoid knowledge disruption caused by one-time pruning.

2.2.3. Knowledge Recovery Mechanism: Accuracy Compensation After Pruning

To minimize performance loss caused by pruning, a knowledge recovery mechanism driven by feature consistency is designed:

a. Feature difference measurement: An intermediate feature cache unit stores the pre-pruning intermediate features

$F_{student}^{l,before}$. The L2 difference between the post-pruning features $F_{student}^{l,after}$ and the cached features is calculated:

$$L_{recover} = \sum_{l \in L_{pruned}} \left\| F_{student}^{l,after} - F_{student}^{l,before} \right\|_2^2 \quad (22)$$

where L_{pruned} is the set of pruned layers.

b. Multi-objective loss optimization: The final total loss is constructed as:

$$L_{total} = L_{student} + \mu L_{recover} + \nu \cdot \|\Theta\|_1 \quad (23)$$

where μ is the knowledge recovery balance coefficient ranging from 0.5 to 2, adjusted dynamically with pruning intensity, and $\nu \cdot \|\Theta\|_1$ is L1 sparse regularization (with $\nu \in [10^{-4}, 10^{-2}]$ and Θ denoting the set of trainable parameters of the network). Network parameters are updated via gradient descent to reduce feature differences and quickly restore the network's expressive capability.

3. Results

3.1. Dataset Design and Construction

3.1.1. Experimental Specimens and Defect Parameters

The experimental data were collected from artificially prefabricated rectangular defects on a Φ 1016 mm large-diameter X70 steel grade natural gas pipeline. The pipeline was divided into five segments: Segments 1, 2, and 5 had a wall thickness of 11.75 mm, Segment 3 had a wall thickness of 13.75 mm, and Segment 4 had a wall thickness of 17.75 mm. The magnetic flux density was strictly controlled at $1.8 \text{ T} \pm 0.05 \text{ T}$, and the lift-off value was fixed at 2 mm, consistent with actual industrial in-line inspection conditions.

The control variable method was used to design defect parameters, ensuring coverage of typical pipeline defect size ranges: (1) Fixing defect width and depth, adjusting length in the range of 10–120 mm at 10 mm intervals; (2) Fixing defect length and depth, dynamically adjusting width in the range of 10–120 mm; (3) Fixing defect width and length, gradually increasing depth from 1 mm to the full wall thickness of the corresponding segment.

The defect size design refers to the Chinese standard Non-Destructive Testing of Pressure Equipment (NB/T standard), with specific correspondences shown in Table 1. The design balances the need to address large defects (length/width > 50 mm)—which, according to Intertek MFL in-line inspection data, critically affect structural integrity and guide RSTRENG repair priorities—with the need to challenge the algorithm using small defects (10–20 mm) near the noise threshold, thereby testing its robustness against background interference. The size classification fully complies with the Chinese national standard GB/T 34370 for MFL testing of pressure equipment.

3.1.2. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The data collection process is shown in Figure 3. An MFL in-line detector equipped with a circularly arranged

Table 1
Definition of NB/T standard dimensions.

Defect type	NB/T standard defines dimensions	Experimental coverage area	Standard detection accuracy requirements
Pinhole	Diameter < 5mm	—	Depth error $\pm 15\%$ @80% confidence level
Groove	Length: 20-50mm, width: 5-20mm	Length: 20-30mm, width: 10-40mm	Length error $\pm 10\text{mm}$, depth $\pm 10\%$
General Loss	Length > 50mm, width > 30mm	Length: 50-120mm, width > 50mm	Area error $\pm 15\%$

Figure 3: Flowchart of experimental sample collection.

Hall sensor array was used for signal collection. The detector operated at a constant speed inside the pipeline; after locating defects, data from 20 groups of sensor probes covering the defect area were selected as the data source, with each probe collecting 100 data points. Since MFL signals include three components (axial, radial, circumferential), the raw data of each defect form a 60×100 2D matrix. After preprocessing steps (denoising, normalization), a 3D interpolation algorithm was used to convert the 2D matrix into a triaxial defect signal image, providing richer spatial feature information for the model.

3.1.3. Dataset Composition and Division

The dataset was constructed following the "simulation-measured-enhancement" trinity principle: (1) 366 groups of industrial on-site measured signals (containing 8–20 dB noise and channel damage) to reproduce real detection environments; (2) 2500 groups of simulated signals generated via MATLAB magnetic dipole models based on the geometric dimensions of 122 actual defects (covering a parameter space of length 10–120 mm and depth 1 mm to full wall thickness) to provide a clean signal source for frequency-domain feature analysis; (3) 2500 groups of data-enhanced samples (by adding random noise and channel damage to real defect data) to improve the model's generalization capability.

All samples had a Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of no less than 15 dB and were divided into training, validation, and test sets using stratified random sampling at a ratio of 7:2:1. To avoid data leakage, all signals from the same physical defect were restricted to one subset, providing a

reliable basis for performance evaluation during distillation and pruning.

3.2. Filter Sensitivity Analysis

Filter sensitivity is the core quantitative basis for adaptive pruning, directly determining the rationality of pruning strategies and the preservation of model performance. Figure 4 illustrates the feature contribution patterns of three types of filters (important, redundant, fluctuating) during training from two dimensions: sensitivity dynamics and sensitivity change rate.

Important filters (Figure 4(a)(b)): Sensitivity increased monotonically with training epochs, remaining above the pruning threshold of 0.4 throughout the process, and the fluctuation range of the sensitivity change rate was controlled within ± 0.2 . This reflects the stability of these filters in continuously accumulating effective defect features. After optimization via Exponential Moving Average (EMA), the average sensitivities in the early (1–15 epochs), middle (16–35 epochs), and late (36–50 epochs) training stages were 0.3596, 0.4709, and 0.6468, respectively, with a final sensitivity of 0.7024 (95.3% higher than the early stage) and a 17.8% reduction in standard deviation. These filters were identified as core components and retained.

Redundant filters (Figure 4(c)(d)): Sensitivity gradually decayed with training epochs, dropping below the pruning threshold in the late stage, and a negative fluctuation of -0.3 amplitude occurred in the middle stage. The declining feature contribution of these filters directly supports their identification as suitable candidates for pruning. The final sensitivity was only 0.2593 (a significant decrease from

Figure 4: Chart of Sensitivity Result Analysis.

the early-stage 0.7730), and the standard deviation only decreased by 7.0% after EMA optimization, with limited stability improvement. These filters were identified as redundant components and pruned.

Fluctuating filters(Figure 4(e)(f)): Sensitivity oscillated irregularly around the threshold, with the sensitivity change rate showing significant positive-negative alternation (maximum amplitude ± 0.4). However, after EMA optimization, the standard deviation decreased by 37.4%, showing the most significant stability improvement. Combined with their final sensitivity of 0.5853, these filters were identified as effective components and retained.

EMA optimization smoothed the sensitivity fluctuation data via weighted averaging, improving the reliability of evaluation results and providing a basis for adaptive pruning.

3.3. General Experimental Analysis

3.3.1. Loss Function Evolution Analysis

Figure 5 compares the evolution patterns of KD loss and classification loss between the proposed method (Ours) and two classical knowledge distillation methods (FitNet, ALC-Net). In terms of KD loss, the proposed method exhibited faster convergence, indicating that the dual-teacher knowledge fusion mechanism and gating strategy effectively improved knowledge transfer efficiency. In terms of classification loss, all three methods showed a monotonic decrease with training epochs, and the proposed method achieved the lowest final classification loss, verifying the promotion effect of multi-dimensional knowledge transfer on defect classification performance.

Figure 5: Chart of KD and Classification loss.

3.3.2. Pruning Strategy Stability Analysis

Figure 6(a)-(d) show the training/validation accuracy and loss evolution curves of the model under different pruning strategies. Overall, the training accuracy of all strategies increased monotonically and approached saturation with iterations, while the validation accuracy fluctuated to a certain extent but remained at a high level. Analysis indicates that while most pruning strategies effectively retain the model's core recognition capability, the DSA strategy alone showed the most pronounced accuracy fluctuations, primarily due to three factors. (1) Multi-modal tasks have high requirements for feature extraction stability; (2) The disturbance of feature space integrity caused by pruning is further amplified by residual connections; (3) The inherent instability of model statistical characteristics under sparse activation mechanisms exacerbates accuracy fluctuations. In contrast, the adaptive pruning strategy proposed in this study dynamically adjusts the pruning ratio based on sensitivity, effectively avoiding the above issues and achieving better stability in both training and validation accuracy.

3.3.3. Comprehensive Evaluation of FROC Index

To quantify the compactness and effectiveness of model feature extraction, this study proposes the Feature Region Occupancy Coverage (FROC) index, defined as the ratio of the feature space region actually activated by the network to the theoretically activable region. The layer weight-weighted normalized FROC score is:

$$FROC - score = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L FROC_l \times \alpha_l \quad (24)$$

where $FROC_l$ is the activation ratio of the l -th layer feature map ($F_l \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$):

$$FROC_l = \frac{\sum_{c=1}^C \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{w=1}^W I(|F_l[c, h, w]| > \tau)}{C \times H \times W} \quad (25)$$

$I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function (1 for activation, 0 otherwise), τ is the activation threshold, α_l is the layer weight

(higher weights assigned to deep features), and L is the total number of network layers.

Figure 7 constructs a multi-dimensional visualization evaluation system using heatmaps, boxplots, and violin plots to compare the performance differences of 7 methods across 5 indicators (average FROC, FROC standard deviation, spatial utilization, channel utilization, feature diversity) from three dimensions: numerical value, distribution stability, and density concentration.

Spatial utilization measures the activation sparsity along the channel dimension in a feature map, reflecting how effectively the model utilizes channel resources to express discriminative features. A lower value indicates that the model can express effective features using only a small number of channels, implying low redundancy, which benefits compression and generalization. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Spatial Utilization} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{\sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{w=1}^W \mathbb{1}(\max_c |F_l[c, h, w]| > \tau)}{H \times W} \quad (26)$$

where $F_l \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$ is the feature map of the l -th layer; $\mathbb{1}(\cdot)$ is an indicator function that equals 1 when the activation value of any channel at a given spatial location exceeds the threshold τ ; τ is the activation threshold; the numerator is the total number of activated spatial locations, and the denominator is the total number of spatial locations; finally, the weighted average across all layers is taken.

Channel utilization measures the activation sparsity along the channel dimension in a feature map, reflecting how effectively the model utilizes channel resources to express discriminative features. A lower value indicates that the model can express effective features using only a small number of channels, implying low redundancy, which benefits compression and generalization.

$$\text{Channel Utilization} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{\sum_{c=1}^C \mathbb{1}(\max_{h,w} |F_l[c, h, w]| > \tau)}{C} \quad (27)$$

Figure 6: Comparison of training and validation accuracy/loss across different methods.

Feature diversity measures the dissimilarity among different activated features, reflecting whether the model extracts rich and diverse features rather than repetitive or redundant patterns. A higher value indicates lower similarity between features across channels, implying more varied and expressive feature representations, which is beneficial for capturing the multi-dimensional attributes of defects.

$$\text{Feature Diversity} = 1 - \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{1}{N_{\text{pairs}}} \sum_{i \neq j} \text{Sim}(F_l^{(i)}, F_l^{(j)}) \quad (28)$$

where $F_l^{(i)}$ is the feature vector (flattened activations) of the i -th channel in the l -th layer; $\text{Sim}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the cosine similarity; and $N_{\text{pairs}} = C \times (C - 1)$ is the number of channel pairs.

The heatmap (Figure 7(a)) shows that the proposed method achieved the optimal values in average FROC (0.3103) and FROC standard deviation (0.036), with the highest feature diversity (0.85 ± 0.037). Its spatial utilization (0.68 ± 0.038) and channel utilization (0.72 ± 0.035) were significantly better than most comparative methods.

The boxplot (Figure 7(b)) reveals that the indicator values of the proposed method were in the dominant position of the corresponding boxes (average FROC below the lower quartile, feature diversity at the top of the whisker), reflecting a better central tendency.

The violin plot (Figure 7(c)) indicates that the proposed method was in the high-optimal density region with small fluctuations across all indicators, verifying the stability and effectiveness of feature extraction.

3.4. Comprehensive Comparison of Defect Recognition Performance

3.4.1. Computational Complexity Comparison

Table 2 compares the parameter count, computational complexity (FLOPs), and inference time of different models. Taking ResNet-18 as the baseline model (11.7 M parameters, 1.8 G FLOPs, 4.8 ms inference time), the proposed FFDT-APNet achieved a parameter count of only 3.5 M (70.1% reduction compared to the baseline, 7.9% reduction compared to the lightweight benchmark DHP), a computational complexity of 0.7 G FLOPs (61.1% reduction compared to the baseline), and an inference time shortened to 2.1 ms (8.7% efficiency improvement compared to DHP). In contrast, the ResNet-101 teacher model, despite improved accuracy, had 44.5 M parameters and an inference time of 22.5 ms, making it difficult to meet embedded deployment requirements. Models such as DenseNet and ALC-Net showed slight accuracy improvements but significantly increased computational overhead. The proposed method realizes the synergistic optimization of complexity and efficiency.

3.4.2. Recognition Accuracy and Confusion Matrix Analysis

Figure 8 shows the confusion matrices of different methods for recognizing radial (Class X), axial (Class Y), and circumferential (Class Z) defects. The overall accuracy ranged from 0.734 to 0.921, showing significant performance differences.

Figure 7: Comparison of FROC metrics across different methods.

Analysis of class-specific performance: Class Y defects exhibited the highest recognition stability (accuracy > 88.1% for most methods), indicating that their features are easy to distinguish. In contrast, the recognition performance of Class X and Class Z defects fluctuated greatly: The accuracy of Class X could reach 100% with some methods but

dropped to 74.3% with others; Class Z defects were severely misclassified by low-performance methods (e.g., 65.2% of Class Z samples were misclassified as Class X in the model with 0.734 accuracy). The significant feature overlap between Class X and Class Z defects poses a considerable challenge, demanding enhanced capabilities in both granular

Table 2
Comparison of computational complexity across different models.

Model	Parameters(M)	FLOPs(G)	Inference time(ms)
ResNet-18 (Baseline)	11.7	1.8	4.8
ResNet-101 (Teacher)	44.5	7.8	22.5
Dense-Net	20.0	4.3	15.2
FITNets	11.7	1.8	4.8
ALC-Net	18.2	3.5	12.3
GCN	9.5	2.1	8.7
DSA	4.2	0.9	2.5
DHP	3.8	0.8	2.3
Ours	3.5	0.7	2.1

Figure 8: Comparison of Confusion Matrix for Defect Recognition.

feature extraction and fine-grained inter-class discrimination from the model.

Performance of comparative methods: ResNet-18 achieved an accuracy of only 0.734, with the core bottleneck being the confusion between Class X and Class Z (65.2% of Class Z samples misclassified as Class X), indicating limited shallow feature extraction capability. The ResNet-101 teacher network improved accuracy to 0.887, with Class X and Class Z recognition accuracy increased by 13.8% and 21.5% compared to ResNet-18, and Class Y recognition accuracy reaching 90.3. This verifies the advantage of deep

networks in enhancing feature discriminability. The GCN network achieved an accuracy of only 0.738 (slightly better than ResNet-18), indicating limited improvement of non-convolutional structures for this task. Pruning methods based on ResNet-18 (DSA, DHP) achieved accuracies of 0.818 and 0.823, respectively, demonstrating that structured pruning can maintain recognition capability while keeping the model lightweight. Classical distillation methods (FitNet, ALC-Net) further improved accuracy to 0.837 and 0.852, reflecting the effectiveness of knowledge transfer in promoting student network learning.

Table 3

Candidate parameter settings based on conventional signal processing choices and MFL signal characteristics.

Index	Window length (samples)	Overlap rate	Window function
A1	32	50%	Hanning
A2	48	50%	Hanning
A3	64	50%	Hanning
A4	128	50%	Hanning
B1	64	75%	Hanning
C1	64	50%	Hamming

Performance of the proposed method: FFDT-APNet achieved the optimal overall accuracy of 0.921, with 100% recognition rate for Class Z, 91.0% for Class Y, and only a small number of misclassifications for Class X. By integrating multi-dimensional knowledge fusion and precise pruning strategies, the method enhances the ability to distinguish confusing features between Class X and Class Z, fully verifying the effectiveness and superiority of the proposed framework.

Radial defect recognition exhibits the largest fluctuation in accuracy and the highest difficulty. This is mainly because its spatial symmetry leads to a high degree of feature overlap with circumferential defects. The frequency-domain energy of radial defects is concentrated in the low-frequency range with a smooth spectrum, making the subtle frequency-domain differences from circumferential defects difficult to fully distinguish. Furthermore, the fine-grained key regions of small-sized and low-contrast defects are even harder to capture, and noise in the measured signals further exacerbates the recognition difficulty. By complementary learning of frequency-domain and fine-grained features, FFDT-APNet effectively alleviates the confusion between the two types of defects, improving radial defect accuracy to 90.2% while achieving high-precision recognition of circumferential defects.

3.5. Ablation Experiment Analysis

3.5.1. Validation of Window Function Parameters for Frequency Domain Teacher Network

We evaluated candidate parameter combinations (window length: 32, 48, 64, 128; overlap rate: 50%, 75%; window function: Hamming, Hanning) using the frequency-domain consistency loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{consist}}^{\text{freq}}$, which measures the robustness of features to noise. As shown in Table 3, the results indicate that the combination of the Hanning window, a window length of 64 samples, and a 50% overlap rate achieves the lowest consistency loss, demonstrating optimal noise robustness.

The evaluation is performed using the frequency-domain consistency loss; a smaller loss indicates stronger noise robustness. Each parameter combination was embedded into the frequency-domain teacher network and trained for 50 epochs within the FFDT-APNet framework. The overall accuracy on the test set and the per class accuracies for the three defect types were recorded. Taking the optimal parameters as the center, we varied the window length and overlap rate

respectively to observe the range of accuracy fluctuation. Table 4 shows the frequency-domain consistency loss on the noise augmented test set for each candidate parameter combination.

Combination A3 (64-point window, 50% overlap, Hanning window) achieves the lowest frequency-domain consistency loss, significantly outperforming combinations with too small or too large windows, indicating that this configuration has the strongest ability to suppress noise interference. When the overlap rate is increased to 75%, the loss rises slightly, possibly because the increased temporal redundancy does not significantly improve feature stability. The Hanning window performs slightly better than the Hamming window, which is consistent with the theoretical property that the Hanning window has faster side-lobe roll-off. Each parameter combination was then embedded into the complete framework to verify its impact on the final recognition performance. As shown in Table 5, it can be observed that the parameters corresponding to A3 yield the best overall performance.

3.5.2. Validation of FFDT-APNet Functional Module

To verify the effectiveness of each core module, five groups of ablation experiments were designed: Ours, Frequency-domain Teacher + Adaptive Pruning (Freq+P), Fine-grained Teacher + Adaptive Pruning (Fine+P), Dual-Teacher Distillation (DT), and Adaptive Pruning (AP). All ablation experiments were conducted under strictly identical experimental conditions, including dataset, training protocol, network initialization, pruning schedule, and evaluation metrics. The only variable across experiments was the combination of modules (frequency-domain teacher, fine-grained teacher, and adaptive pruning). The adopted evaluation metrics are pruning recovery speed and accuracy. Pruning recovery speed is defined as the number of training epochs required for the model to recover to its pre-pruning validation accuracy through subsequent training after a pruning operation. This metric quantifies the degree to which a pruning strategy preserves the core knowledge structure and the effectiveness of the knowledge recovery mechanism. In the specific calculation, after each pruning operation, the number of epochs required for the validation accuracy to first return to the pre-pruning level is recorded; the values presented in Table 6 are the averages of the recovery speeds across all pruning rounds. A smaller recovery speed indicates that the pruning strategy better retains critical feature channels and

Table 4
Frequency-domain consistency loss of different window function parameters.

Parameter combination	Window length	Overlap rate	Window function	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{consist}}^{\text{freq}}$
A1	32	50%	Hanning	0.124 ± 0.018
A2	48	50%	Hanning	0.103 ± 0.015
A3	64	50%	Hanning	0.087 ± 0.011
A4	128	50%	Hanning	0.094 ± 0.013
B1	64	75%	Hanning	0.101 ± 0.014
C1	64	50%	Hamming	0.095 ± 0.012

Table 5
Final recognition performance of different parameter combinations.

Parameter combination	Overall accuracy	Radial (X)	Axial (Y)	Circumferential (Z)
A1	0.896	0.872	0.908	0.908
A2	0.912	0.894	0.921	0.921
A3	0.921	0.902	0.931	0.931
A4	0.914	0.891	0.926	0.926
B1	0.918	0.896	0.928	0.928
C1	0.916	0.894	0.925	0.928

that the knowledge recovery mechanism is more effective. The results are shown in Table 6, Figure 9, and Figure 10.

The stacked bar chart (Figure 9) shows that the proposed method (DT+P) achieved a comprehensive score of 1.78 (accuracy \approx 0.92 + efficiency \approx 0.86), significantly outperforming other variants. Among the comparative methods, ‘‘Fine+AP’’ had relatively high accuracy (\approx 0.85) but insufficient efficiency (\approx 0.75), while ‘‘Adapt Only’’ showed the worst performance in both accuracy (\approx 0.70) and efficiency (\approx 0.72).

The radar chart (Figure 10) provides a normalized evaluation of multiple distillation-pruning methods across 6 dimensions: final accuracy, convergence speed, training stability, pruning robustness, model efficiency and sparsity utilization. The proposed method exhibited balanced and excellent performance across all dimensions, with core indicators (convergence speed, pruning robustness, model efficiency) approaching or exceeding 0.9. In contrast, the other comparison methods have obvious shortcomings: for example, the DT network and the AP network score below 0.5 in some dimensions; while the combinations of Freq+P and Fine+P underperform in terms of model efficiency and sparsity utilization.

Ablation experimental results indicate that the synergistic effect of DT+AP is the key to performance improvement. Single modules or partial combinations cannot achieve optimal results, verifying the rationality of the network architecture design.

4. Discussion

4.1. Engineering Value and Technical Advantages of Core Innovations

FFDT-APNet targets two persistent challenges in MFL defect recognition: the difficulty of balancing high accuracy

with a lightweight architecture and the inadequacy of single-dimensional feature representations. To this end, it introduces a tripartite solution: dual-teacher collaborative distillation, adaptive pruning, and a collaborative optimization mechanism. These innovations yield technical and engineering benefits in three principal aspects.

(1) The dual-teacher knowledge distillation framework breaks the limitation of traditional single spatial-domain knowledge transfer, fully exploiting the frequency-domain physical information and spatial fine-grained features of MFL signals. The frequency-domain teacher extracts defect frequency components and energy spectrum patterns via DCT and STFT, and incorporates frequency-domain consistency loss to enhance noise robustness (adapting to noise interference in industrial on-site measured data). The fine-grained teacher captures local defect details and contextual associations via the SCA attention module and prototype contrast learning, strengthening the feature representation of small targets and low-contrast defects. The knowledge gating fusion mechanism dynamically adjusts the distillation weights of the dual teachers, effectively alleviating conflicts between different knowledge sources and realizing adaptive complementation of multi-dimensional knowledge. The aforementioned mechanism underpins the method’s notable accuracy, notably in challenging cases involving the confusable Class X and Class Z categories.

(2) The adaptive pruning strategy embedded in the distillation process abandons the traditional separate ‘‘pruning-then-distillation’’ paradigm. A multi-dimensional sensitivity evaluation matrix is used to quantify filter importance, and EMA optimization and progressive pruning are combined to ensure that the pruning process does not damage the core knowledge structure. The knowledge recovery mechanism measures the difference between feature maps before and after pruning and updates parameters via gradient descent to

Table 6

Comparison of final accuracy and pruning recovery rate.

Method	Freq+P	Fine+P	DT	AP	DT+AP(Ours)
Final accuracy	95.3	95.5	94	90.2	98.8
Pruning recovery speed	24.6	26.9	22	35.2	23.8

Figure 9: Accuracy and efficiency stacked comparison.

quickly compensate for performance loss caused by pruning. This enables the model to achieve a 70.1% parameter reduction (compared to ResNet-18) while improving accuracy by 18.7%, laying the foundation for embedded in-line inspection device deployment. This helps extend device battery life, improve single-segment pipeline inspection efficiency, and reduce the engineering cost of oil and gas pipeline operation and maintenance.

(3) The collaborative optimization loop of "knowledge-guided pruning and pruning-promoted learning" realizes deep coupling between modules. The distillation process provides precise knowledge guidance for pruning to ensure only redundant components are removed; after pruning streamlines the network structure, the student network's parameter updates focus more on core feature channels, improving knowledge absorption efficiency. Ablation experiments verify that the complete scheme (DT+P) achieves a final accuracy of 98.8%, significantly outperforming single-module combinations and providing a new paradigm for lightweight model design in complex industrial scenarios.

4.2. In-Depth Analysis of Experimental Results and Limitations

Experimental results demonstrate the superior performance of FFDT-APNet in MFL defect recognition. While promising, the approach is subject to several limitations: a. Although the dataset includes industrial measured, simulated, and enhanced samples, the defect types are mainly rectangular prefabricated defects. Extending the evaluation to encompass the complexity of irregular natural corrosion defects found in field conditions represents a critical next step for conclusively establishing the model's generalization ability; b. The pruning strategy is based on multi-dimensional sensitivity evaluation but does not consider the specificity of defect types (e.g., different requirements of small and large defects for filter importance). A dynamic pruning ratio adjustment mechanism adaptive to defect types can be introduced in subsequent studies; c. The actual deployment effect of the model on embedded devices still needs to be verified via hardware testing. Further optimization of model inference speed and memory usage is required to adapt to in-line inspection devices with different computing power levels.

Figure 10: Ablation experiment radar comparison chart.

4.3. Future Research Directions

This study lays the groundwork for several promising avenues of future investigation, which include the following directions:

(1) Expansion of multi-modal knowledge fusion: Combining other non-destructive testing signals (e.g., ultrasonic, eddy current) to construct a cross-modal dual-teacher distillation framework, further improving the comprehensiveness of defect representation;

(2) Synergistic optimization of pruning and quantization: Introducing low-bit quantization technology based on adaptive pruning to realize "compression-quantization" dual lightweighting of the model, further reducing deployment costs;

(3) Adaptation to few-shot learning: Addressing the problem of scarce defect samples in industrial scenarios, combining meta-learning with dual-teacher distillation to improve the model's recognition performance under few-shot conditions and expand the scope of technical application.

5. Conclusion

Aiming at the massive data processing requirements of ultra-high-definition pipeline MFL in-line inspection and the computing power constraints of embedded devices, this study proposes a FFDT-APNet. Through a synergistic closed-loop framework integrating multi-dimensional knowledge fusion with dynamic structural optimization, FFDT-APNet addresses the long-standing trade-off between high accuracy and model lightness, and overcomes the limitation of insufficient feature representation inherent in

single-dimensional approaches. The principal findings of this study are summarized as follows:

(1) The dual-teacher knowledge distillation framework effectively improves the comprehensiveness and accuracy of defect feature representation. The frequency-domain teacher and fine-grained teacher extract global frequency-domain features and spatial local features of defects, respectively. The knowledge gating fusion mechanism realizes dynamic complementary knowledge transfer, enabling the defect recognition accuracy to reach 92.1%—18.7% higher than the baseline ResNet-18 (73.4%), 8.4% higher than FitNet (83.7%), and 6.9% higher than ALC-Net (85.2%). The recognition rate of circumferential defects reaches 100%, reducing the risk of missed and false judgments in engineering scenarios.

(2) The adaptive pruning strategy realizes a balance between efficient model compression and performance preservation. Based on multi-dimensional sensitivity evaluation of filters, the progressive pruning and knowledge recovery mechanism compress the model parameter count to 3.5 M (70.1% reduction compared to ResNet-18), reduce computational complexity to 0.7 G FLOPs (61.1% reduction), and shorten inference time to 2.1 ms (8.7% efficiency improvement compared to the lightweight benchmark DHP), meeting the deployment requirements of embedded devices.

(3) The collaborative optimization mechanism breaks the limitation of the traditional separate "pruning-distillation" paradigm. Dual-teacher knowledge distillation provides precise guidance for pruning, and pruning streamlines the network structure to promote efficient knowledge absorption, forming a collaborative optimization loop. The ablation

study validates the complete scheme, which achieves a final accuracy of 98.8%, significantly outperforming any single-module combination. This result thereby establishes a reliable technical solution for pipeline MFL in-line inspection with considerable engineering application value.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luyao He: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Yurong Zheng:** Investigation, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Bin Liu:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Jiawen Zhang:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Jing Rao:** Supervision. **Liang Yang:** Resources, Validation.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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